

ROLE OF CIRCULAR TRAINING IN FORMING STUDENTS' INFORMATION COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *In this article, the group activities in the general secondary school contribute to the full development of the individual, to identify and develop the creative abilities of the growing young generation, to inculcate hard work in students, and to use the free time of students wisely. instructions for use are provided.*

Keywords: *circle, extracurricular activities, qualification, knowledge, quality of education, national program, information technology, process, principle.*

The training of qualified pedagogic specialists largely depends on their methodological training. In particular, it is an extremely difficult process to convey and form complex information to the minds of students. The school program is not limited to providing students with knowledge in school subjects, but also assumes the formation of necessary skills and competences in them. It is necessary for each student to acquire knowledge independently based on the skills and competencies acquired in the lesson.

In order to organize the activities of general education institutions and raise the quality of education to higher levels, "Concept of the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", "Additional measures for the further improvement of the education system" on events" decision, Presidential decree "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" , "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" decrees were passed. In these important documents, while giving in-depth knowledge to students, they showed different ways of preparing them for life, developing informational competence and training them for professions .

In accordance with the national program in our country, regular education of students at all stages of general secondary education, development of enthusiasm for learning, work skills, independent creative thinking, conscious attitude to career choice and environment. the tasks of education, respect for national and universal values, loyalty to one's country, people, and love were defined.

The effectiveness of the work of the circle largely depends on how the plan is structured. The circle should have its own journal or diary. It is good that the members of the circle also have a separate diary. The teacher reflects the students' interest in the diary, the form and methods of conducting it, students' independence, and difficult questions. A bibliography is also displayed in the diary. The circle can be held once every month or once every 15 days. The circle consists of branches. Affiliate refers to a part of a larger circle.

The methodology of extracurricular activities in education is closely related to the system of subjects and serves as the basis for the methodology of the subject. Information technology is of great importance in forming the knowledge, skills and abilities of students in the formation of the content of the science.

The methodical integration of educational technical tools in the teaching of extracurricular activities in the subject of information technology in general education schools of our republic increases the working time and interest of students in science. Full and thorough mastering of the circle activity requires students to have certain theoretical and practical knowledge.

In this regard, the skills of knowing, being able to manage and having imagination are formed. In particular, through the didactic analysis of knowledge, educational and technical tools, the ability to logically analyze the educational material, the analysis of each concept in the educational material form the basis of theoretical methods. In particular, researching the relationship between the teacher's activity and the student's activity, the goal and the content of the training, and the relationship between the educational methods and the upbringing makes the basis of the theoretical methods external. First of all, it is necessary to theoretically analyze special educational technical tools and literature in order to define the goals and objectives of the relevance of the methodological problem. If we want to look for effective methods and means of formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications, we should first start with the analysis of the educational process. This can be done on the basis of experiments, teaching, using questionnaires, and organizing circle activities in the form of interviews with students and teachers.

Circle work read the students to diligence, forward put to the goal in achieving the worldview expanding, communicative, creative and cognitive abilities in development help gives.

While studying in circles, students get deeper knowledge on the topic they are interested in, develop their personal potential, plan their free time effectively. Also, training in circles makes the student more disciplined, teaches him to organize himself.

And quizzes are held in clubs for schoolchildren. It helps to maintain interest in lessons, to express one's thoughts in different circles. In addition, methods such as interview, essay, lecture, excursion, practical work, experiment and observation are used.

N.M. Pochikeeva calls one of the main methodological principles of the organization of group classes to be the replacement of different types of student activities.

The second important methodological principle is the interesting organization of group and individual work. In this, the student shares the work to be done, feels personal responsibility and contributes to this process.

Another important methodological component is the ability to establish relationships with members of the circle and teachers. It helps to form children's communication skills, forms a positive attitude to cooperation and educates the social orientation of the child's personality.

- circle classes are based on several basic principles:
- in each new lesson, each participant of the work should learn something new and useful for himself and share this information with others:
- in the lesson, students should be able to present the studied material, show each other the mastered work methods, that is, this is the principle of continuous transfer of knowledge.
- in the circle, everyone is constantly learning from each other, that is, the principle of continuous transfer of knowledge is implemented
- in circles, everyone works together, helps each other, that is, the principle of universal cooperation and mutual assistance is manifested
- students consciously approach learning the given educational material. The teacher should maintain their interest and activity by using active teaching methods.

A positive educational process can only be achieved if the team of pedagogues strives to keep pace with time and children, learns to work creatively based on their experience, as well as the achievements of pedagogy sides begin to appear.

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